

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTISTIC TEXTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH

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Abstract: In this article, scientific opinions are given about the importance of artistic text and work on the text in the development of speaking ability of elementary school students. Erkin Vahidov's poems suitable for children are selected as a sample. Ways of analyzing the text are given to the reader.

Key words: context, artistic analysis, method, discourse richness, comparative analysis.

Introduction.

By working on the artistic text, to develop the connected speech of children, to develop their oral speech, to learn the main content of the text, and to analyze the characters and natural scenes in the text; imagery characteristic of artistic texts; the image of different people is at the center of the work of art, that is, fiction is anthropology; that the images are images of people or other objects, animals in the work; they artistically embody human characteristics and express his psyche, feelings, character traits, good or bad qualities; it should be explained in a simple way that the lyrical hero's experiences and feelings take the lead. We recommend working with the text based on the same requirements while studying the poem "Olka". First, the teacher recites the poem expressively. With the help of reciting, one can transmit the feelings expressed in the poem, love for the Motherland, love for the country. For the first time, they will have the opportunity to emotionally understand the artistic thought expressed in the poem - its idea. Starting with the verse "*When I walked through your gardens, you were in my heart, my country*", attention is paid to the fact that the feeling of the country grows in the heart of every person from infancy. From the moment a baby steps on the earth for the first time, he gets to know its beauties, can enjoy them, taste its blessings, and love them. Even a thousand different trees growing on the motherland seem to praise her for taking root in this land. Expressing his imagination to the poet, the poet wrote: "... *Millions of eyes are looking at your happiness from the blue.*"

Any answers of the children to the questions leading to the analysis of the poem should be accepted, they should be filled in by the educator. It is important

that they imagine and enjoy the poetic image in the poem, understand its meaning, and be able to express the thoughts born from their imagination.

Speech development is one of the core issues of preschool education. Children's speech takes place in the family, in preschool educational institutions, in the community in the form of exchange of ideas, conversation, dialogue, debate on a specific topic, and question-and-answer. Speech is expressed in oral and written forms. When the thinking, perception, imagination, and feelings of the pupils of preschool educational institutions are stimulated, speech becomes a means of expressing these thoughts. In pre-school education, it is possible to transfer the thoughts that have arisen as a result of mental and emotional influence on the child to a specific form of speech in thinking. Therefore, the process of turning thought into a form related to the child's psyche is considered a psychological aspect of the issue. Emotions and thoughts arise quickly in impressionable children, but in such a case they have difficulty finding the form of expression of thoughts immediately. As a result, they express their thoughts in a fragmented, disorganized, hasty way, and make a number of mistakes in their speech.

Although the influence of children who stay away from arguments, who do not like to argue, who prefer to stay "on the other side" of the circle rather than engage in open communication, and who are "observers" is slow, they listen to the opinions of their friends, they can react after comparing their views. Children belonging to this category are not in a hurry to express their opinion and do not show their emotions clearly. Some children think and answer the question asked by the teacher without haste; they strive to express their thoughts fluently, meaningfully, logically and effectively in oral speech. With such children, parents attach enough importance to working with books in the family. As a result, they love works of art, fairy tales, especially love listening to works of art. Due to their connected speech, they are highly developed, they have a high thinking capacity, a consistent style of expression, and their oral speech is developed and meets standard requirements.

We recommend to read and study the poems "Apple" and "Cherry" by the national poet Erkin Vahidov in small groups, taking into account the effect of these poems on the imagination of children and the psyche of 3-4-year-old children. The poem is written in a simple artistic language, and because of the use of figurative tools such as revitalization, simile, and quality, apples and cherries seem to speak to the little reader, to not stop in their rawness, and then, like Nortoji, say, "Oh, my stomach, - don't stay!" - he calls not to get into an

unpleasant situation. Cherry also "says" her adjectives one by one, as if inviting children to be sweet and tasty like her. And the verse "If you find it, wear my pair in your ear" expresses the custom of children, the joyous mood, childish fun. This method transforms the pupil from inactivity into a participant in the educational process, a partner of the educator who is actively thinking and doing practical work.

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In general, the content and form of the poem chosen for children should be appropriate and specific to their psychology.

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